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ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
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Yakubova Oltinoy Abduganievna,

doctor of Medical Sciences of the Department of obstetrics-gynecology, orthopedics-traumatology, neurosurgery, sports medicine, faculty of advanced training and retraining of doctors, Andijan State Medical Institute, docent

Isakova Dilnoza Bakhtiyarovna,

PhD of the Department of Obstetrics-gynecology, orthopedics-traumatology, neurosurgery, Sports Medicine, Faculty of Advanced Training and retraining of Doctors, Andijan State Medical Institute, docent

Suleymanova Nasiba Adashevna.

candidate of medical sciences of the Department of obstetrics-gynecology, orthopedics-traumatology, neurosurgery, Sports Medicine, Faculty of Advanced Training and retraining of doctors, Andijan State Medical Institute, docent
nadjmitdinova@mail.ru

CUTTING-EDGE ADVANCEMENTS IN EARLY DETECTION, PREVENTION, AND PROGNOSTICATION OF PRECANCEROUS AND CANCEROUS CONDITIONS OF THE CERVIX

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ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer (CC) is among several oncological conditions that, if detected early, can be successfully treated, leading to higher overall survival rates, reduced chances of recurrence, enhanced quality of life for patients, and lower treatment costs. The primary cause of cervical cancer is oncogenic strains of the human papillomavirus (HPV), which can be prevented through screening tests.

Keywords: Cervical diseases, oncogenic strains of HPV, minimally invasive techniques, and early detection.

Якубова Олтиной Абдуганиевна,

доктор медицинских наук кафедры акушерства-гинекологии, ортопедии-травматологии, нейрохирургии, спортивной медицины, факультет повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей, Андижанский государственный медицинский институт, доцент

Исакова Дилноза Бахтияровна,

кандидат медицинских наук кафедры акушерства-гинекологии, ортопедии-травматологии, нейрохирургии, спортивной медицины, факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей, Андижанский государственный медицинский институт, доцент

Сулейманова Насиба Адашевна.

кандидат медицинских наук кафедры акушерства-гинекологии, ортопедии-травматологии, нейрохирургии, спортивной медицины,

факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей,
Андижанский государственный медицинский институт, доцент

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ В РАННЕМ ВЫЯВЛЕНИИ, ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ И ПРОГНОСТИКЕ ПРЕДРАКОВЫХ И РАКОВЫХ СОСТОЯНИЙ ШЕЙКИ МАТКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Рак шейки матки (РШМ) относится к числу онкологических заболеваний, которые при раннем выявлении поддаются успешному лечению, что приводит к повышению общей выживаемости, снижению вероятности рецидивов, повышению качества жизни пациентов и снижению затрат на лечение. Основной причиной рака шейки матки являются онкогенные штаммы вируса папилломы человека (ВПЧ), появление которых можно предотвратить с помощью скрининговых тестов.

Ключевые слова: заболевания шейки матки, онкогенные штаммы ВПЧ, малоинвазивные методы, раннее выявление.

Yakubova Oltinoy Abduganievna,
tibbiyot fanlari doktori, Andijon davlat tibbiyot instituti vrachlar malakasini oshirish va qayta tayyorlash fakulteti Akusherlik -ginekologiya, ortopediya -travmatologiya, neyroxirurgiya, sport tibbiyoti kafedrasini, dotsent.

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tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi, Andijon davlat tibbiyot instituti vrachlar malakasini oshirish va qayta tayyorlash fakulteti Akusherlik -ginekologiya, ortopediya -travmatologiya, neyroxirurgiya, sport tibbiyoti kafedrasini, dotsent.

BACHADON BO'YNI SARATONI VA SARATONDAN OLDINGI HOLATLARNI ERTA ANIQLASH, OLDINI OLISH VA PROGNOZLASH BO'YICHA ILG'OR YUTUQLAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Bachadon bo'yni saratoni bir qancha onkologik kasalliklar qatoriga kiradi, ular erta aniqlansa, muvaffaqiyatli davolanadi, bu umumiy omon qolish darajasining oshishiga, takrorlanish ehtimolining pasayishiga, bemorlarning hayot sifatini oshirishga va davolanish xarajatlarini kamaytirishga olib keladi. Bachadon bo'yni saratonining asosiy sababi odam papilloma virusining onkogen shtammlari bo'lib, ularni skrining tekshiruvlari orqali oldini olish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Bachadon bo'yni kasalliklari, odam papilloma virusining onkogen shtammlari, minimal invaziv usullar va erta aniqlash.

Relevance: Cervical cancer (CC) is a condition that can be effectively prevented. Topical treatments for preinvasive cervical lesions, known as high-grade cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (HG CIN), have been established as a clinically relevant strategy. It's been shown that the progression from human papillomavirus (HPV) infection to CC can span 15-20 years[1,3]. Such a long precancerous phase provides opportunities for early diagnosis and timely therapy, making it possible to express the imperative about the advisability of population screening. Despite the introduction of population screening, invasive cervical cancer remains one of the most common malignant diseases - the fourth most common malignant neoplasm in women, according to world statistics. In 2018, cervical cancer was diagnosed in 570,000 women and caused death in 311,000. At the same time, 84% of cases and 88% of deaths from cervical cancer occur in developing countries [3,4]. In countries with a highly organized healthcare system, there is a significant reduction in morbidity and mortality

from cervical cancer as a result of the treatment of precancerous lesions identified during the screening process [5,6].

Also, screening activities make it possible to identify cases of cancer, which, with timely interventions, can reduce cancer mortality. In the UK, the incidence of cervical cancer has decreased by 24% since the introduction of the national screening program in 1988 [1,9]. Mortality decreased from 8/100 thousand in 1988 to 3/100 thousand women in 2017 [1,9]. Since the introduction of population screening in Finland in 1960, morbidity and mortality have decreased by 80%. Today, the incidence is 4/100 thousand and the death rate is 1/100 thousand women per year [5]. Trends in the dynamics of morbidity and mortality in different countries depend on various factors, including the prevalence of HPV infection, the environmental situation, and the quality and volume of screening programs. In the mechanism of oncogenesis, both environmental factors and changes in hormonal status, toxic effects, and viral infections are essential [7]. These factors disrupt the epigenetic regulation of the cell cycle by methylation of promoter genes and inhibition of oncogenesis suppressor genes [2,8].

Over the past decade, there has been significant progress in the prevention of cervical cancer in connection with the inclusion of testing for the presence of HPV DNA in screening programs, as well as in connection with the introduction of preventive HPV vaccination. Clinical and morphological classification of pathological processes of the cervix, proposed by Ya.V. Bohman in 1989, includes 5 types of lesions [2]:

1) background processes: ectopia, true erosion, ectropion, polyp, endometriosis, leukoplakia, erythroplakia, papillomas and flat warts

2) precancerous process - cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN):

- CIN1 - weak

- CIN2 – moderate

- CIN3 - heavy

3) preinvasive cancer (Ca in situ, intraepithelial cancer)

4) micro-invasive cancer

5) invasive cancer: squamous keratinizing, non-keratinizing, adenocarcinoma, dimorphic glandular-squamous (mucoepidermoid), poorly differentiated.

The importance of clinical and morphological classification is determined by its key role in the choice of patient management tactics: local treatment methods (cytotoxic drugs, chemical and physical destruction) are possible only with pre-invasive types of lesions. Invasive cancer requires surgical removal, as well as the use of polychemotherapy and radiation therapy [3,7].

WHO also proposes classifying cervical epithelial dysplasia by degrees as low, moderate and severe: CIN1, CIN2, and CIN3, respectively.

Exfoliative cytology has been the mainstay of pathology screening for a long time. Traditionally, cells were obtained by smear with a special brush or spatula. The material was placed on glass (slide) and stained according to the method proposed by Papapikolaou in the 40s of the 20th century (Pap smear). The liquid cytology method has recently been used, in which the material is collected with a plastic brush immersed in a special fixation solution. Equipment for obtaining cytological material is approved for use by the responsible authorities of various countries, including the reputable American Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Liquid cytology has many advantages over the Pap smear:

- diagnostic slides are received in a semi-automatic mode,

- cell debris, erythrocytes, leukocytes and artifacts are removed during the smearing process - a thin layer of epithelial cells is formed, available for qualitative visual analysis by a morphologist,

- In addition to cytological examination, the obtained material can be used for PCR HPV testing and determining other molecular markers.

Liquid cytology reduces the proportion of low-quality slides from 9.1% to 1.6% [10]. The meta-analysis, conducted during the preparation of the European Guidelines for Quality Assurance in Cervical Cancer Screening, showed that although liquid-based cytology and traditional pap smear show comparable diagnostic sensitivity and specificity characteristics in terms of detecting

CIN stage 2 and above (CIN2+) and also that liquid cytology is less specific in terms of detecting atypical cells of indeterminate significance (ASC-US), liquid cytology improves the quality and speed of interpretation, as well as other molecular tests [8].

A limitation of cytology is the large number of false negative results (20%-25%). This phenomenon is associated with both the disadvantages of obtaining diagnostic slides and errors in their interpretation [8].

A retrospective analysis shows that in most cases (60%), the primary diagnosis of cervical cancer is recorded in women who do not have clinical manifestations of the disease, i.e., in the screening process, in 10% of cases, the disease is diagnosed at the stage of clinical manifestations due to insufficient screening programs. However, 30% of new cases of cervical cancer are not detected during the screening process (false-negative cytological results). In addition, cytological examination is ineffective in detecting intraepithelial lesions of the glandular epithelium located in the endocervical glands [118]. This is due to the difficulty of reaching the surface parts of the glands during sampling; as a result, these cells do not enter the test material. The incidence of epithelial pathology and adenocarcinomas progressively increases and accounts for 20-30% of all cases of cervical cancer. This type of cervical cancer shows a significantly worse prognosis, in particular, due to late diagnosis and detection at a higher clinical stage.

Purpose of the study. To develop an algorithm of step-by-step actions for the early detection of precancerous diseases of the cervix.

Material and research methods. Various methods are used in the diagnosis of precancerous diseases and cervical cancer: clinical-visual, extended vulvovaginal and colposcopy; cytological; liquid cytology; molecular genetic (viral genotyping, expression of viral oncoproteins E6, E7); determination of viral load Hybrid Capture (Digene-test); morphological study; immunocytochemical and immunohistochemical study of markers p16, Ki67; optical-electronic scanning of cervical tissue (TruScreen); anoscopy (using a colposcope). Our study included 130 patients with pathological changes in the cervix of varying degrees associated with HPV, such as cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) and underlying cervical disease. We used a minimally invasive method in the form of a CIN-DIAG solution, which has a sensitivity of 98% and a specificity of 95% to determine pathological changes in the early stages of development. It is a sterile test tube with a tupper (a long spatula with a cotton/viscose swab at the end). The clinical sensitivity and specificity of the CIN-DIAG solution proved to be no worse than other methods. In an analysis of 130 cervical cytological specimens from the screening population, of which 58 were from women with CIN2+, the test showed a relative sensitivity and specificity for CIN2+ of 0.98 and 1.00, respectively. HPV-based screening can detect persistent high-grade cervical lesions before conventional cytology, providing 60–70% greater protection against invasive cervical carcinomas compared to Pap smear [11]. In addition, we have demonstrated that the performance of the CIN-DIAG test on self-collected vaginal specimens is as good as that obtained on clinician-collected cervical specimens (relative sensitivity 0.92 and relative specificity 0.97). Finally, with this method, we can describe the prevalence of HPV types in the study population.

Results. The solution enters the cell with the help of folic acid through a specific effect on cell surface receptors. As a result of a specific reaction of the dye solution with the chemical substance of the histiocyte, the tampon is stained. There is a low active oxygen content in normal cells, so there is little expression of folic acid receptors on the cell surface and no tampon staining after the reaction. Analysis of the test results showed the following results: CIN1 - 32 (33.3%), CIN 2 - 58 (12.5%), CIN 3 - 12 (8.3%), cervical cancer - 8 (4.1%), background diseases of the cervix 70 (29.1%) and 30 (12.5%) women without pathological changes, i.e. negative result. Discussions. Cervical cytology has been used for many years as the standard screening test for cervical cancer. However, it has some potential limitations: the conventional staining procedure requires a significant amount of time and consumables, and the Pap smear process is characterized by poor reproducibility and errors in interpretation due to blood and slime[6,14].

Moreover, it requires a cytologist for analysis, with increased costs and the need for a proper parameter. HPV-based screening helps detect persistent high-grade cervical lesions before

conventional cytology, providing 60% to 70% greater protection against invasive cervical carcinomas than a Pap smear. CIN-DIAG solution may be an attractive solution to increase participation in screening for opportunistic cervical cancer regardless of age, educational level, and other possible social parameters. To the question, "Was the procedure easy?" 98.26% of women answered in the affirmative. Conclusion: This minimally invasive method for early detection of cervical cancer complies with all international guidelines, has been clinically tested for primary screening of cervical cancer and has been approved for self-sampling.

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